

BLUECOAT

Sustainable coating for challenging conditions

BIO-SUSHY

Memorandum of Understanding

for the operations of the

Circular, Sustainable, and Biobased Coating Cluster

(Version 3.0)

History of Changes

15 October 2025	Version 1.0	First consolidation for signature
20 January 2026	Version 2.0	Addition of BIO-SUSHY
20 April 2026	Version 3.0	Addition of SuperBark

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1. Aim and Objectives

The Cluster provides a collaborative platform for its members to share and exchange information, and to implement joint or coordinated activities that maximise impact and support the successful delivery of each project's objectives.

The Cluster aims to:

- Facilitate the further development and implementation of **biobased coating materials for applications under demanding and/or extreme conditions.**
- Enable a better understanding of the research challenges on **biobased coating materials.**
- Support further improvement by promoting the use of **biobased coating materials** across different applications.
- Enable evidence-based policy and decision-making based on the results of the clustered projects.

2. Value proposition of the Forum

This Cluster shall strive to bring added value to its individual members by providing:

- Access to shared relevant, non-confidential, technical, and scientific information across Cluster members.
- Maximised impact of Cluster member activities through scientific exchange across the clustered projects.
- Optimised use of budgetary resources to convene technical meetings and workshops/webinars focused on issues of common interest.
- A common voice and point of contact in representing Europe's leadership in further development and implementation of the biobased coating materials in Europe and globally.

3. Membership

3.1 Founding members

The initial members and co-leads of the Cluster are:

- European Bioplastics e.V.
- The BIO4COAT project is represented by its coordinating organisation, Funditec.
- The BLUECOAT project is represented by its coordinating organisation, University of Birmingham.
- The SUPREME project is represented by its coordinating organisation, University of Birmingham.

BIO4COAT and BLUECOAT have been funded under the call HORIZON-JU-CBE-2024-RIA-04 SSbD bio-based coating materials for applications under demanding and/or extreme conditions. SUPREME has been funded by the call HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-20 - Antimicrobial, Antiviral, and Antifungal Nanocoatings (RIA). These projects are referred to as "clustered projects".

3.2 Representation

Each project in the Cluster is represented by the project' coordinators and /or their project partners.

3.3 Joining the Cluster as a member

The following initiatives and projects can join the Cluster:

- EC-funded or co-funded projects actively contributing to the implementation of the circular, biobased and sustainable coating materials.
- Other EU and non-EU initiatives actively contributing to the implementation of the circular, biobased and sustainable coating materials.

These may join the Cluster via an expression of interest submitted to the Cluster Facilitator.

3.3 Tasks

The Cluster members commit to collaborating on activities that align with its aims and objectives and to dedicating time to them accordingly.

3.4 Withdrawal and Termination from membership

Members may withdraw from the Cluster at any time by written notification to the Facilitator.

As projects conclude their activities, the organisations will automatically cease to be members of the Forum, unless otherwise indicated.

4. Cluster Facilitator

European Bioplastics e.V. acts as a Cluster Facilitator. The Facilitator serves as a central point of contact for entities wishing to engage with the Cluster and its members collectively, and for prospective projects and initiatives interested in joining the Cluster.

The Facilitator tracks the progress of Cluster activities. A list of Forum members and their contact details is maintained by the Cluster Facilitator.

5. Governance

The Cluster is an informal cluster of projects and initiatives, and as such, it has no legal entity or formal decision-making authority.

5.1 Lead

The Cluster is led by the Cluster Facilitator with the support of the BIO4COAT, BLUECOAT, and SUPREME coordinators.

5.2 Working Groups

Clustered projects may form ad hoc working groups to address specific topics, activities or events. Such groups are temporary and composed of relevant individual experts from project partner organisations or other relevant initiatives. They are facilitated by the Cluster Facilitator. The working group activities must be linked to one of the activities under § 6 and attached to a specific task for specific outputs.

6. Activities and potential outputs

The Cluster facilitates a range of activities and potential outputs such as:

- Joint technical discussions (online and/or in person) under the coordination of the Facilitator.
- Joint webinars (at least 10) with experts from the project partners and the clustered projects, under the coordination of the Facilitator.
- Two Technical Workshops under the coordination of the Facilitator: One in-person and one online. The Technical Workshops are joint networking events with other EU-funded projects to exchange technical knowledge.
- Periodic joint meetings between the clustered projects to exchange information, advice, and updates, at least once per year (online), facilitated by the Facilitator.
- Drafting joint scientific publications.
- A joint policy briefing, under the coordination of the Facilitator, providing a synthesis of outcomes and recommendations stemming from individual projects and initiatives.
- Joint contribution to policy initiatives, such as replies to Commission consultations or contributions to white papers.
- Invitation of the clustered projects' representatives to others' annual meetings to share updates.

7. Entry into force, lifetime and legacy

The Cluster is established by the agreement of this MoU by its initial members, European Bioplastics e.V., BIO4COAT, SUPREME and BLUECOAT.

This MoU comes into force upon agreement by EUBP and the coordinators of the three projects.

The Cluster may be disbanded and cease to exist at any time by agreement of its members.

The Cluster will cease to exist upon the completion of all projects that constitute its members, unless planned handovers are in place.

8. Resources

The Cluster has no resources or funds of its own. It relies on in-kind contributions from its members, supported by their funds or other resources (e.g., funds from participating projects).

9. Revision of this MoU

This MoU may be revised at any time by agreement of its members.

10. Cluster Facilitator Contact

Contact with the Cluster is via the Cluster Facilitator:

Name: European Bioplastics

Chiara Bearzotti and Estela Lopez-Hermoso

Email: euprojects@european-bioplastics.org

List of Cluster members

European Bioplastics e.V.

[BIO4COAT](#)

[BLUECOAT](#)

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[BIO-SUSHY](#)

[SuperBark](#)